

INFLUENCE OF CONSTRUCTIVE DEVIANT BEHAVIOUR ON WASTE MANAGEMENT OPERATION IN PORT HARCOURT, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the possible influences of constructive deviance on waste management operation in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The study was a descriptive analysis. Three research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The simple random sampling technique was utilized and sample size of thirty (30) was chosen. The Least Square and Multiple Regression Analysis were used for the organization of data. The result indicated that organization effectiveness is not a function of constructive deviance. Also, there was a negative relationship between deviance behaviour targeting waste management agency and organizational performance. Thus, it is recommended that waste management agency should encourage constructive deviance behaviour to enhance and promote organizational performance and efficiency in the waste management operation in Port Harcourt.

Keywords: waste management, constructive deviance, organizational effectiveness.